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RBI GUIDELINES – SUPPORT OR SETBACK ANALYSIS OF RBI GUIDELINES DURING SUB-PRIME CRISES

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Abstract

US Sub-prime crises was the latest financial debacle to hit the global economy. In this era of globalization it would not be untrue to say that every country was directly or indirectly affected by this global crisis. Current paper discusses the role played by RBI at the time when central bank's role as a regulator was prime importance. Specifically this paper has analysed the guidelines issued by the RBI during 2007 sub-prime crises which had severe after effects on the strongest of economies of the world

Reserve Bank, the central bank of India has a prime responsibility of governing business and economy in India. It has to play a role which regulates and also gives out new growth opportunities to new businesses. These two require a very good balance in the restrictions and prospects posed by RBI on the corporate sector. All this is generally done through the banks which in turn are controlled by the RBI – the apex body which creates the monetary policy of Indian republic. RBI gives out policies to commercial banks and other financial institutions about the kind of financial products they can create in terms of risk and returns that they offer to the investors.

This paper is written after a detailed study of RBI guidelines on working of commercial banks in light of the global recession which witnessed fall of big economies like US, Europe and institutions like Lehman Brothers, Bear Sterns which were once regarded as immortals.

Key words: RBI, Setback Analysis, Financial Products

Objectives of the Study

The two basic objectives of the study were -

1. To analyze whether RBI guidelines proved to be a support or setback for commercial banks to survive during the recession.
2. To come across the effects of guidelines issued by RBI to cope with the global problem of recession.

Research Methodology

Data was collected by both primary and secondary sources. In total 200 questionnaires were filled by employees of different public and private sector banks of Jaipur. Data collected was analysed with the help of graphs, percentage and chi square. The level of significance taken is 5% in this case.

Hypothesis

H₀ = There is no significant difference between the opinion of bank employees regarding the effects of RBI guidelines on operations of commercial banks.

H_a = There is a positive difference between the opinion of bank employees regarding the effects of RBI guidelines on operations of commercial banks.

Analysis of Data

Variable (Q)	Calculated Value	Critical value	Null Hypothesis
Q.1 Cost of undertaking guidelines	8	.455	Rejected
Q.2 Autonomy	13.12	7.82	Rejected
Q.3 Change in investment preferences post Sub-prime crises	92.48	.455	Rejected
Q.4 Compliance a hindrance for banks	108.63	5.99	Rejected
Q.5 Intensity of monitoring by RBI	18.24	7.82	Rejected
Q.6 Higher Capital Adequacy Ratio	32	.455	Rejected
Q.7 RBI's support to fight recession	37.4	7.82	Rejected
Q.8 Higher Collateral reduce NPA	108.47	5.99	Rejected
Q.9 Higher banking rates reduce NPA	109.51	5.99	Rejected
Q.10 Stricter RBI guidelines reduce NPA	51.52	7.82	Rejected

Testing of Hypothesis

All the questions asked in the questionnaire can be divided into 4 basic categories which are –

- Effect of Recession on Indian Banking Sector
- Monitoring by Reserve Bank
- Suitability of Action of Reserve Bank During the Recession
- Compliance and Guideline Issues

Now let us discuss all these points at length.

1. Effect of Recession on Indian Banking Sector – North India came out to be the most affected region according to the respondents. As the crisis resulted in stock market volatility so the domestic corporate sector was affected badly out of all the sectors like domestic retail, domestic corporate, NRI retail and NRI corporate. There also Corporate Borrowing was the most affected area of business for the banks.

2. Monitoring by Reserve Bank - When bankers were asked about the monitoring of banking operations by the RBI a clear answer was that RBI should ease out the day to day working of the commercial banks as such intensive monitoring and interference hinders the working of subordinate banks and increases their operating costs to a large extent. Unanimously all the respondents felt that banks should be given more autonomy in their working.

3. Suitability of Action of Reserve Bank during the Recession – When asked about the appropriateness of actions taken by the RBI during recession most respondents were of the view that the monetary policy measures taken (Repo, reverse repo, CRR, SLR) did not prove to be a lot of help as they do not effect directly. But stricter guidelines did control the situation to a lot of extent.

4. Compliance and Guideline Issues - Reserve Bank follows a very conservative approach in its guidelines. The reserve requirements and the paper work required by RBI is much more than the International standards. According to all the respondents this approach is very useful for them and has helped in reducing their NPA's. But on the hind side frequent changes in the guidelines have a negative impact on the efficiency of the banks.

According to the above analysis of data the RBI guidelines are proving supportive to commercial banks in facing recessionary period.

Findings

1. After the debacle of 2007 in stock exchange, investor's inclination has increased towards safer avenues than equity markets. This resulted in introduction of more innovative products by banks to lure the general public. These new products are safer and generally offer fixed return.

2. High exposure to collateral has reduced non-performing assets. India follows very strict policy regarding collaterals against loans. It is obvious that if a person has given a security against a loan which could be liquidated in case of non-payment of interest and principle then he would be extra cautious regarding the payment of both interest and principle amount. That is why there are less NPA's in Indian banking sector.

3. With a unanimous vote all the respondents said that changes in monetary policy has no effect on reducing NPA's of banks. Monetary policy measures include increase in repo, reverse repo, SLR, and CRR.

4. Strengthening of guidelines issued by RBI helps in reducing NPA's of banks. Strengthening of guidelines includes improving Know Your Customer Norms and customer's credit history check.

5. RBI guidelines helped in insulating Indian banks from any kind of global financial crises. It has strengthened the Indian banks with rigid norms so that banks always have some safety money with them at all times.

Recommendations

1. Systematic Surveillance System - The banks should not base their loans on some mathematical models as they can go wrong, rather they should keep a close surveillance system through which the current position and status of than be borrower can be traced.

2. Credit History Analysis of Borrowers Should be Made Essential - If a borrower has been a defaulter in the past then his chances of being defaulter in the future increases. So the check on a borrower's credit history is very important. The lender should fully document a borrower's ability to repay the home loan. The lender should do a full verification of all sources of a borrower's income.

3. Greater Need for Consumer Protection - A standard regarding the suitability should be considered for mortgage borrowers and lenders. This means that there should be a standard which helps both the parties to analyses whether it is appropriate to lend to this customer and it is safe to borrow on the stipulated terms and conditions. There is a need to have better disclosure practices for mortgage products like the detail of teaser rates, interest –only payments etc should be clearly and effectively communicated to potential borrowers. So that they can get an idea whether they would be able to bear the burden of the loan and would be able to repay it back.

4. Securitas Should Be Rated Very Professionally - The system should invent such a process in which there is a uniform way of rating securities. Rating agencies should put in place automated and objective systems, based on the changing value of underlying asset, to continuously re-rate debt structures. Training and qualification standards for rating analysts should be prescribed, to help create consistent, objective, transparent and reliable methods.

5. Long Term Strategies Should be Formulated and Minimal Changes to Suit Market Conditions Should be Adopted - All stakeholders should b made aware that the basic framework will remain same and they should plan accordingly. In those long term plans only small manipulations should be made to suit the current scenario.

6. RBI Should Pass and Monitor the Products Designed by the Banks – The Global recession of 2007 saw that very risky products were introduced by the banks and other such institutions which led to downfall of the whole US economy. RBI should be proactive and should investigate and see that all the new and existing financial products are customer friendly and not too risky to handle.

Conclusion

Gdseradual opening of the Indian economy on the one hand filled the resource gap; on the other hand it has made economy prone to shocks originating in other parts of the world. Global crisis spilled over in India through financial as well as real channels. Because of limited exposure of Indian banks to distressed assets, India was not directly affected by the financial crisis, but the indirect effects through trade and capital flows were severe. Indian government in coordination with RBI responded with several policy measures to minimize the impact of the crisis. Although,

policymakers have been successful in containing the crisis, some policy concern still remains which will have to be addressed.